

Analysis with Box-Behnken design for Methyl Blue dye removal by inorganic-organic hybrid containing Tyrosine

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Article Info	Abstract
Oral Presentation Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14332392	This study examined the efficacy of removing methyl blue from aqueous solutions inorganic-organic hybrid containing tyrosine as an adsorbent. The characterization of the synthesized adsorbent was evaluated by FT-IR analysis. Employing a batch system, the influence of pH, initial dye concentration, and amount of adsorbent on the adsorption of methyl blue was examined via Response Surface Methodology (RSM) predicated on Box-Behnken design (BBD) modeling.
Keywords Adsorption Box-Behnken Inorganic-Organic hybrid Methyl Blue Tyrosine	

1. Introduction

Dyes have been used to color clothes and fabrics since the earliest periods of human history. Studies on the development of synthetic dyes as well as natural dyes have increased and the understanding of the production of dyes has expanded.

Famous chemical factories in Europe used dye production as a means of transition. However, due to the fact that there are very few companies producing dyes in Turkey and there is not much interest, this problem is tried to be solved by importing dyes [1].

Dyes can show acidic, basic or neutral properties according to their chemical structure and the electrical charges they contain. These properties directly affect the efficacy and use of dyes in various application areas. Researchers often use different methods to classify dyes based on their specific properties and application requirements. Therefore, the classification of dyes may vary depending on the specific purpose. However, the most common and comprehensive classification method is the system that divides dyestuffs into six main categories according to their basic properties [2].

This system provides many advantages in both scientific studies and industrial applications by grouping the chemical and physical properties of dyestuffs in an organized way. In particular, this classification makes it possible to better understand the properties of dyestuffs and

to use them more effectively according to specific application requirements [3,4].

2. Materials and Methods

UV-Vis spectrophotometer (T80+ UV/VIS Spectrometer. PG Instruments Ltd) was used for maximum wavelength scanning of dyes and quantitative determination of dye concentrations for dye removal.

All glassware was soaked in acidic washing solution at least overnight before use and then rinsed with distilled water. The distilled water used was obtained from Elga Purelab Flex 1-2 Ultra pure water and has a conductivity of 18.2 μ s.

The pH values of the solutions were determined with Hanna Instruments pH 211 Microprocessor model pH meter. pH meter was adjusted with NBS buffer solutions before each use. In adsorption processes, 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M NaOH solutions were used to adjust the pH values of the solutions.

Stock dyestuff solutions (1000 mg/L) used in the experimental studies were prepared by taking 1000 mg of Methylene Blue and dissolving in deionized water. Methylene Blue dyes were obtained from Merck. Dyestuff solutions with different initial concentrations were obtained and used by diluting the stock solutions to the desired ratio.

The BBD modeling technique was employed to discern optimal process conditions of variables that yield the most favorable responses. The identification of optimal adsorption conditions hinged on the maximization of

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pivotal operational parameters. ANOVA analysis was conducted to ascertain the degree of parameter effectiveness.

This study underscores the prominence of inorganic-organic hybrid containing tyrosine as an economical and potent adsorbent in the context of methyl blue removal [5].

3. Results and Discussion

Before determining the optimum conditions, we determined the interactions between the factors.

Factors and their interactions were identified with the pareto chart of the standardized effects.

The "Dye" concentration stands out as the most important factor. It is the only factor that exceeds the $\alpha=0.05$ significance level shown by the red line in the graph.

Since the other factors are below the significance level, they do not have a statistically significant effect.

The most critical parameter in the dye removal process is the dye concentration. The effect of other experimental parameters on the process is not statistically significant. But the factor's interactions are significant.

Figure 1. Pareto Chart of the Standardized Effects.

The Box-Behnken design was used to design the optimal conditions and find a pH of 10, 4.5 mg adsorbent, and 5 ppm dye concentration.

Multiple Response Prediction

Variable	Setting
pH	10
mg Adsorbent	4.45455
ppm Dye solution	5

Response	Fit	SE Fit	95% CI	95% PI
%R	39.82	3.42	(32.69; 46.95)	(26.17; 53.47)

Figure 2. Multiple Response Prediction.

Analysis of variance was performed. The purpose of ANOVA is to use the differences in variance between different groups to test whether the means of those groups are statistically significantly different. That is, it compares

the variance within a group and the variance between groups to understand how much a factor or interaction in the experiment affects the response variable. The p-value, together with the resulting test statistic (F-value), assesses whether this result is random. If the p-value is less than 0.05, this indicates that there is a significant difference between the groups, and the hypothesis is rejected. That is, the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable.

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Model	9	1901.04	211.227	6.78	0.000
Linear	3	1524.80	508.265	16.32	0.000
pH	1	880.61	880.606	28.28	0.000
mg Adsorbent	1	4.10	4.101	0.13	0.720
ppm Dye solution	1	640.09	640.090	20.56	0.000
Square	3	263.40	87.800	2.82	0.065
pH*pH	1	27.01	27.010	0.87	0.363
mg Adsorbent*mg Adsorbent	1	117.42	117.417	3.77	0.066
ppm Dye solution*ppm Dye solution	1	101.10	101.095	3.25	0.087
2-Way Interaction	3	112.85	37.616	1.21	0.332
pH*mg Adsorbent	1	26.65	26.645	0.86	0.366
pH*ppm Dye solution	1	31.60	31.601	1.01	0.326
mg Adsorbent*ppm Dye solution	1	54.60	54.601	1.75	0.200
Error	20	622.71	31.136		
Lack-of-Fit	3	570.54	190.181	61.97	0.000
Pure Error	17	52.17	3.069		
Total	29	2523.76			

Figure 3. Analysis of Variance.

Since the p-value of the model is $0.000 < 0.05$, the model is statistically significant. pH: has a significant effect since the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$. mg Adsorbent: has no significant effect since the p-value is $0.720 > 0.05$. ppm Dye solution: has a significant effect since the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$.

The most important factors are pH and dye solution concentration. The amount of adsorbent alone has no significant effect. The interactions between the factors are not significant. The model is sufficient to explain the data.

Figure 4. Surface Plots of %R

The surface plot shows the effect of pH and adsorbent amount on the response variable. The shape of the plot helps us to determine the interaction of these two factors

and the optimum conditions. The response variable seems to reach its maximum value at the intermediate pH values and in the region where the adsorbent amount is high. The response variable decreases when the pH is very low or very high. As the adsorbent amount increases, the response variable generally increases, but this increase slows down after a certain point. This plot provides valuable information on how to adjust the pH and adsorbent amount to optimize the adsorption process. This surface plot visualizes the effect of pH and adsorbent amount on the dye removal or adsorption process and helps to determine the optimum operating conditions.

The Main Effects Plot visualizes the effect of each independent variable (factor) on the dependent variable (e.g. %R, i.e. yield). This plot allows us to understand the independent influence of each factor and the direction of its effect on the response variable.

Main Effects Plot is a powerful tool that visualizes the main effect of each independent variable (factor) on the response (e.g. %R). By comparing response values at different levels of the factors, this graph helps you determine which factors have more influence on the response. The slope of the lines and the differences between the levels tell you about the magnitude of the influence of the factors.

Figure 5. Main Effects Plot for %R

The X-axis shows the amount of adsorbent.

The line shows an almost horizontal trend. This shows that the amount of adsorbent does not have a significant effect on the response variable. The change in the amount of adsorbent does not cause a significant change in the response variable.

The X-axis shows the dye concentration. The line has a significant slope. This shows that the dye concentration has a significant effect on the response variable. As the dye concentration increases, a significant change is observed in the response variable.

The graph shows the effects of two factors (adsorbent and dye) independently. The effect of the dye concentration is much more pronounced than the effect of the amount of

adsorbent. These results show that the dye concentration is a more critical parameter in process optimization. The optimization of the amount of adsorbent seems to be of secondary importance.

This graph supports the ANOVA and Pareto analysis results we have seen before and once again emphasizes the importance of the dye concentration in the process.

Figure 6. Main Effects Plot for %R

4. Conclusions

The combination of the organic component (Tyrosin) and the inorganic part in the structure of our hybrid material provides interactions that improve the adsorption process. Tyrosin plays an important role in this process by strongly supporting various mechanisms (ionic bonds, hydrogen bonds) that act on dyes.

When we analyzed the effects of Box-Behnken experimental design on the removal of Methyl Blue dye, we observed that pH, adsorbent amount, and dye concentration were the most significant factors. The highest dye removal efficiency was obtained at pH 10, 4.5 mg, and 5.0 ppm dye concentration. Under these conditions, 35.1% of Methyl Blue was removed.

As a result of these results, low dye removal was observed. In future studies, the material should be improved or a different type of dye should be used to increase this removal.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declares that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that

could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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